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A posteriori variances for least-squares estimates with weight reduction

by L Lindegren

This note, triggered by a question by P C Hansen and C Petersen (letter of 7/9/87), contains some primitive considerations about the practical calculation of output uncertainties in least-squares solutions. The main problem is a certain ambiguity inherent in the estimation process especially when there is a great redundancy of observations (as is often the case for Hipparcos): On one hand, one has some *a priori* estimate of the uncertainty of input data ('observations'), and on the other, one may obtain a completely independent estimate at least of the overall uncertainty of the observations from the residual statistics. Ideally, the two estimates should agree within the statistical uncertainties of the estimates themselves, but in practice one will often find a significant discrepancy. (Usually, the residuals from the least-squares fit are a bit larger than expected, perhaps due to a slightly inadequate model or a tendency to underestimate the uncertainty of the observations.) The question then arises whether and how to adjust the uncertainties of input and/or output data according to this indication. A further complication is how to deal with weight-reduced observations in this connection. The following considerations are put forward for discussion.

The least-squares problem is cast in the standard form

$$\underline{z} = \underline{A} \underline{x} + \underline{e}, \quad E(\underline{e}) = \underline{0}, \quad E(\underline{e}\underline{e}') = \underline{I} \quad (1)$$

where $\underline{z}$ is the n -vector of observations, $\underline{x}$ the m -vector of model parameters ($n \geq m$), $\underline{A}$ the $n \times m$ design matrix, and $\underline{e}$ the n -vector of observation errors. Two remarks should be made before we proceed. First, most processing problems are in fact non-linear, in which case (1) must be a linearized (and therefore more or less approximative) version of the problem. $\underline{x}$ is then the correction to some initial parameter vector and $\underline{z}$ is the deviation of observed values from the ones predicted for the initial parameters. Secondly, the 'raw' observations $\underline{z}$ usually have a covariance matrix $\underline{C}$ different from unity. Provided that $\underline{C}$ is well-conditioned, we then perform a weight-normalization according to $\underline{z} = \underline{C}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \underline{z}$, where $\underline{C}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ is the inverse of some square root of $\underline{C}$, in order to fulfil the last identity in (1). If the raw observations are uncorrelated (diagonal $\underline{C}$), this process simply amounts to dividing each raw observation equation by the *a priori* standard deviation of that observation. We also assume that $\underline{A}$ has full rank, $\text{rank}(\underline{A}) = m$.

The least-squares estimate $\hat{\underline{x}}$, which minimizes the euclidean norm $\| \underline{z} - \underline{A}\underline{x} \|$, is formally obtained as

$$\hat{\underline{x}} = (\underline{A}'\underline{A})^{-1}\underline{A}'\underline{z} \quad (2)$$

and an unbiased estimate of its covariance is given by the inverse normal equations matrix $(\underline{A}'\underline{A})^{-1}$. [In practice $\hat{\underline{x}}$ may be computed e.g. by orthogonal transformations, which is numerically better but mathematically equivalent to (2).] The corresponding estimate of the error vector ('residual') is

$$\hat{\underline{e}} = \underline{z} - \underline{A}\hat{\underline{x}} = [\underline{I} - \underline{A}(\underline{A}'\underline{A})^{-1}\underline{A}']\underline{e} \quad (3)$$

Thus, $E(\hat{\underline{e}}) = \underline{0}$ and $E(\hat{\underline{e}}\hat{\underline{e}}') = \underline{I} - \underline{A}(\underline{A}'\underline{A})^{-1}\underline{A}'$ according to the last two identities in (1). Also, it can be shown that the expected value of the residual sum of squares, $RSS = \hat{\underline{e}}'\hat{\underline{e}}$, is

$$E(\hat{\underline{e}}'\hat{\underline{e}}) = \text{trace}[E(\hat{\underline{e}}\hat{\underline{e}}')] = \text{rank}[\underline{I} - \underline{A}(\underline{A}'\underline{A})^{-1}\underline{A}'] = n - m \quad (4)$$

(since $\underline{I} - \underline{A}(\underline{A}'\underline{A})^{-1}\underline{A}'$ is symmetric and idempotent). In fact, if the errors are gaussian, $\underline{e} \sim N(\underline{0}, \underline{I})$, then RSS has the chi-square distribution with $n - m$ degrees of freedom,

$$RSS \sim \chi_{n-m}^2 \quad (5)$$

so that

$$E(RSS) = n - m, \quad \text{Var}(RSS) = 2(n - m) \quad (6)$$

(5) can obviously be used to test the model fit, although other tests (e.g. of residual correlations in case of a polynomial or spline model) may be more powerful for this purpose. So far this is all standard stuff.

Now suppose that all the different tests indicate that the fitted model is adequate, but the RSS is still too small or too large when compared with the expected distribution (5). We may then conclude that the *a priori* variances of the observations were systematically overestimated or underestimated, respectively, so that the last identity in (1) does not hold. A natural remedy is then to adjust the *a priori* covariance matrix by a suitable scaling factor. Simple scaling has the advantage that the least-squares estimate $\hat{\underline{x}}$

is not affected, only its estimated covariance is scaled by the same factor. Thus, there is no need to repeat the least-squares process. Let f be the scaling factor, so that we assume

$$E(\underline{ee}') = \underline{I}.f \quad (f > 0) \quad (1')$$

instead of (1). The estimated covariance of $\hat{\underline{x}}$ is then

$$\text{Cov}(\hat{\underline{x}}) = (\underline{A}'\underline{A})^{-1}.f \quad (7)$$

How should we compute the scalar f ? There are two extreme possibilities: If we rely entirely on the *a priori* variances, then we should retain $f = 1$. On the other hand, if we rely entirely on the residual statistic (RSS), then $f = \text{RSS}/E(\text{RSS}) = \text{RSS}/(n-m)$ is the proper scaling factor (which would make the scaled RSS equal to its expectation, $n-m$). In practice some compromise between these two extremes may have to be found, mainly depending on the degrees of freedom (or observation redundancy) $\nu = n-m$. For if ν is very large, then RSS/ν is a fairly reliable estimate of the mean variance per observation, and a scaling factor close to RSS/ν is very reasonable. If $\nu = 0$, then $\text{RSS} = 0$ also and we have no choice but to rely on the *a priori* variances. The relative uncertainty of RSS/ν can be estimated as $\sqrt{(2/\nu)}$ from (6).

It seems difficult to define an automatic procedure for calculating f without somehow introducing the notion of the *a priori* uncertainty of the *a priori* assumption of $f = 1$. My proposal is to assign a definite value α to the relative uncertainty of the *a priori* variances, and then calculate the final f as a weighted mean of 1 and RSS/ν , where the weights are inversely proportional to the squares of the relative uncertainties. Thus,

<i>a priori</i> value of $f = 1.0$,	weight = α^{-2}
indicated f -value = RSS/ν ,	weight = $\nu/2$

$$\text{weighted mean: } f = (\text{RSS} + c)/(\nu + c), \quad c = 2\alpha^{-2} \quad (8)$$

It is my feeling that variance estimates are seldom more accurate than 10 to 20 %, which would make $c \sim 100$ in (8). My proposal is to use (8) with $c = 100$ for calculating f , in the absence of any other relevant information.

It remains to discuss how to treat weight reductions in this scheme. As an example, consider the 'Danish method' in which the initial weight of each observation is reduced by the factor

$$w(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & |t| \leq \ell \\ e^{-|t|/\ell} & |t| > \ell \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where t is the normalized residual from the previous adjustment and ℓ is a suitable limit (usually $\ell = 3$). For the present discussion we may identify t with the components of $\hat{e}$, although it should strictly speaking include a further factor from the *a posteriori* covariance matrix $\underline{I} - \underline{A}(\underline{A}'\underline{A})^{-1}\underline{A}'$ (this factor is normally close to 1 if ν is not too small). The adjustment is iterated until the weights do not change any further. Let $\tilde{x}$, $\tilde{e}$ denote the solution and residual vector after convergence of this procedure. We have

$$\tilde{x} = (\underline{A}'\underline{W}\underline{A})^{-1}\underline{A}'\underline{W}\underline{z} \quad (10)$$

$$\tilde{e} = \underline{z} - \underline{A}\tilde{x} \quad (11)$$

$$\underline{W} = \text{diag}[w(\tilde{e}_1), w(\tilde{e}_2), \dots, w(\tilde{e}_n)] \quad (12)$$

$$\text{RSS} = \tilde{e}'\underline{W}\tilde{e} \quad (13)$$

$$\nu = \text{trace}(\underline{W}) - m \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Cov}(\tilde{x}) = (\underline{A}'\underline{W}\underline{A})^{-1} \frac{\text{RSS} + c}{\nu + c} \quad (c = 100) \quad (15)$$

Equations (13) and (14) modify the RSS and ν in a reasonable manner (note however that ν is no longer integer) for the ensuing calculation of the output covariance by means of (15). In particular, if a few of the residuals are very large, so that $w(\tilde{e}_i) \approx 0$ for these, while $w(\tilde{e}_j) = 1$ for the other residuals, then (10) - (15) is exactly equivalent to deleting the observations with large residuals.

Finally it can be noted that if the output is the fitted observables rather than the model parameters (e.g. the smoothed attitude rather than the spline coefficients), then these should be computed as

$$\tilde{z} = \underline{A}\tilde{x}, \quad \text{Cov}(\tilde{z}) = \underline{A}(\underline{A}'\underline{W}\underline{A})^{-1}\underline{A}' \quad (16)$$